

=====

**School Heads’ Leadership And Supervisory Skills:
Their Relationships to Teachers’ Performance**

=====

Dr. Riggi L. Lachica

Principal IV Department of Education, Division of Bacolod City, Philippines
<https://orcid.org/0009-0002-1950-4308> | riggi.lachica001@deped.gov.ph

Abstract:

School leadership and supervisory skills play a central role in determining school effectiveness. School leadership is defined as a blend of several tasks mostly related to instructional efforts leading to academic excellence. In these present times, supervision does not only aim to inspect or evaluate teachers’ performance but it moves its direction into a technical process which is aiming for the continuance of teachers’ development. This study aimed to determine the school head’s leadership and supervisory skills and their relationship to teachers’ performance of public elementary schools in the Division of Bacolod City during the School Year 2016-2017. The variables considered were Age, Sex, Length of Service and Highest Educational Attainment. In terms of leadership skills, the areas included were Administrative Skills, Interpersonal Skills, and Conceptual Skills. In terms of Supervisory Skills, the areas considered were Quality Assurance, Technical Assistance and Monitoring and Evaluation. The result of the study showed the following: the level of school heads’ leadership skills in terms of administrative skills, interpersonal skills and conceptual skills were all at very high level. The level of school head’s supervisory skills in terms of quality assurance, technical assistance and monitoring and evaluation were all at very high level. The level of teachers’ performance in all areas was interpreted as very satisfactory. They performed the greatest in the area of teaching-learning process while least in the area of community involvement. The school heads’ leadership skills in the areas of administrative skills and conceptual skills as assessed by teachers were all at very high level in all issues. There was no significant difference in the level of school heads’ leadership skills in the area of administrative skills when they were grouped and compared according to aforementioned variables. There was a significant relationship between the level of school heads’ supervisory skills and level of teachers’ performance.

Keywords: Leadership, School Head, Supervisory Skills, Teachers Performance

Introduction:

“Tell me who your principal is and I will tell you what kind of school you have” the popular saying of the former Assistant Schools Division Superintendent Luisito J. Escalona, Ed.D. This spell out the broad duties and responsibilities of a school head under his leadership to improve the school. Great school leaders must be visionary, community builder, and emotional intelligent.

A visionary leader talks and walks the school's vision. His actions consistently align with it. A head of school who is a community builder knows that he cannot implement the school's vision alone. You will know if you are entering a healthy community by the way you are greeted as you arrive on campus - by security guards, office staff, children and parents. Emotional intelligence (EQ) is the ability to understand and manage your own emotions and recognize, understand and manage the emotions of others. Emotional intelligence in a leader has been found to be the number one predictor of an organization's ability to be successful (Aguilar, 2014).

Glickman et al (2010) described supervision as a “glue” of a successful school. Instructional supervisory skill of the principal is key to the improvement of quality education in any school and leads to enabling students perform well in their academics (Solomon, 2015).

At the beginning of school year, school heads and teachers agree on the alignment of their efforts in the attainment of the same target – improvement of key performance indicators. These are enumerated in the Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) signed by the teachers to commit themselves to accomplish such. Efforts in the attainment of these targets are clearly stated in the different Key Result Areas with objectives to be rated according to quality, efficiency and timeliness. Numerical values on the accomplishments at the end of school year will be quantified using the rubrics agreed upon by both parties (Division Memorandum No. 186, series of 2017). From the foregoing premises, the researcher is inclined to investigate whether or not school heads’ leadership and supervisory skills has a relationship with teachers’ performance in the hope to provide significant information that will be the basis for crafting plans, programs and activities for enhancement of school heads.

Hence, it is important for the researcher to determine if he has possessed the necessary leadership and supervisory competence to lead and manage the school for personal and professional growth and development. The realization of the Department of Education's vision and mission motivated the researcher to conduct this study.

Objectives of the Study

This study aimed to determine the school heads' leadership and supervisory skills their relationships to teachers' performance of public elementary schools in the Division of Bacolod City during the School Year 2016-2017.

Specifically, this study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of the following variables?
Teachers:
 - a. Age
 - b. Sex
 - c. Length of service as a teacher
 - d. Highest educational attainmentSchool heads:
 - a. Age
 - b. Sex
 - c. Length of service as school head
 - d. Highest educational attainment
2. What is the level of school heads' leadership skills as assessed by teachers and by themselves in terms of the following areas?
 - a. Administrative Skills
 - b. Interpersonal Skills
 - c. Conceptual Skills
3. What is the level of school heads' supervisory skills as assessed by teachers and by themselves in terms of the following areas?
 - a. Quality Assurance
 - b. Technical Assistance
 - c. Monitoring and Evaluation
4. What is the level of teachers' performance in terms of the following areas?
 - a. Teaching-learning process
 - b. Learners' outcome
 - c. Community involvement
5. What is the level of school heads' leadership skills as assessed by teachers and by themselves when they are grouped according to the aforementioned variables?
6. What is the level of school heads' supervisory skills as assessed by teachers and by themselves when they are grouped according to the aforementioned variables?
7. What is the level of teachers' performance when they are grouped according to the aforementioned variables?
8. Is there a significant difference in the level of school heads' leadership skills when grouped and compared according to aforementioned variables?
9. Is there a significant difference in the level of school heads' supervisory skills when grouped and compared according to aforementioned variables?
10. Is there a significant difference in the level of teachers' performance when grouped and compared according to aforementioned variables?
11. Is there a significant relationship between the level of school heads' leadership skills and level of teachers' performance?
12. Is there a significant relationship between the level of school heads' supervisory skills and level of teachers' performance?

Literature Review:

Leadership is the art or process of influencing people so that they strive willingly and enthusiastically toward the achievement of group goals. It is a complex task and requires knowledge, experience and good skills. There is no generic definition of school principal but it concerns practices and operations of educational management. The field of educational management relates varying approaches and established disciplines including economics, general management, psychology, sociology and political science. Good health management is expected to produce planned work done with the help of assigned people, within the allocated budget and within the given deadlines. Education institutions require management to plan, organize, direct, control and evaluate day-to-day activities to accomplish education goals through coordination education personnel and allocated budgets (Farah, 2013).

Managerial skills are set of qualities and attributes in a personality of the managers that enable them to effectively manage the working of the organization. It can also be defined as specialized technical knowledge in certain jobs that

managers should possess to perform their duties and roles by education where by people can be equipped with skills. Managerial skills are acquiring and learning abilities. In other words, we can say that managerial skills are a set of behaviors that lead to effective job performance (Kamete, 2014).

The principals' administrative skills and management of school resources is bound to affect teachers' effectiveness and invariably the students' performance. These skills could be in the areas of communication, school plant management as well as supervision (Oleforo, Antigha & Essien, 2017).

Research Method:

This section presents the research design, the selection of subject respondents, the data-gathering procedure, research instrument, validity and reliability of the research instrument, and data gathering procedure. Likewise, it presents various statistical tools to be used in analyzing the data gathered.

Research Design

This study aimed to find out the school heads' leadership and supervisory skills their relationships to teachers' performance. Thus, from the nature of the study, it required the use of the descriptive research design. Pagano (2011) explained that descriptive research design is appropriate for studies which aimed to find out what prevail in the present conditions or relationships, held opinions and beliefs, processes and effects and developing trends.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of this study were three hundred thirty (330) teachers and school heads of 46 public elementary schools in the Division of Bacolod City during the School Year 2016-2017.

Table 1
Distribution of Respondents

District	Name of Schools	Teachers			School Head
		Population	Percent (%)	Sample (n)	
District 1	ABES 1	48	2.55	8	1
	ABES 2	52	2.76	9	1
	ABKASA ES	23	1.22	4	1
	Banago 1 ES	65	3.45	11	1
	Banago 2 ES	28	1.49	5	1
	Mandalagan ES	41	2.18	7	1
District 2	A Montelibano ES	21	1.12	4	1
	Bata 1 ES	61	3.24	11	1
	Bata 2 ES	30	1.59	5	1
	CL Montelibano ES	57	3.03	10	1
	Estefania ES	54	2.87	9	1
	Isla ES	14	0.74	2	1
	Montevista ES	39	2.07	7	1
District 3	A Arceo ES	12	0.64	2	1
	A Lizares ES	52	2.76	9	1
	A Mabini ES	55	2.92	10	1
	FF Gonzaga ES	23	1.22	4	1
	Fr. Gratian Murray IS	20	1.06	4	1
	Patricia Homes ES	37	1.97	7	1
	R Alunan ES	20	1.06	4	1
	VAGRES	44	2.34	8	1
District 4	AL Jayme ES	76	4.04	13	1
	Cabugwason ES	16	0.85	3	1
	Felisa ES	22	1.17	4	1
	G Lopez Jaena ES	35	1.86	6	1
	Handumanan 1 ES	88	4.68	15	1
	Handumanan 2 ES	34	1.81	6	1
	J Gonzaga ES	40	2.13	7	1
	Paglaum Village ES	32	1.70	6	1
District 5	CV Ramos ES	33	1.75	6	1
	E Garcia ES	33	1.75	6	1

	JR Torres ES	68	3.61	12	1
	Puentevella ES	24	1.28	4	1
	Rizal ES	72	3.83	13	1
	SPED Center	6	0.32	1	1
	Vista Alegre ES	21	1.12	4	1
District 6	ETCS 1	66	3.51	12	1
	ETCS 2	61	3.24	11	1
	ETCS 3	64	3.40	11	1
DISTRICT 7	Sum-ag ES	97	5.15	17	1
	I Nessia ES	31	1.65	5	1
	R Medel ES	71	3.77	12	1
	FR Flores ES	28	1.49	5	1
	Villa Esperanza ES	19	1.01	3	1
	M Medalla IS	31	1.65	5	1
	Pahanocoy Baybay ES	18	0.96	3	1
Total		1,882	100.00	330	46

Data-gathering Instruments

The data gathering instruments used in this study were self-made questionnaires relevant to the school heads' leadership and supervisory skills. Areas covered in leadership skills were administrative skills, interpersonal skills and conceptual skills while areas covered in supervisory skills were quality assurance, technical assistance and monitoring and evaluation.

The instruments consist of two parts:

Part I of the instruments consist of the profile of the respondent such as age, sex, length of service as school head or teacher and educational attainment.

Part II of the instruments are the questionnaire proper relevant to the school heads' leadership skills in the areas of administrative skills, interpersonal skills and conceptual skills; and, supervisory skills in the areas of quality assurance, technical assistance and monitoring and evaluation. The respondents were given options to respond to the questions by ticking under columns 1, 2, 3, 4 or 5 on the spaces provided after each question interpreted as Very Low Level, Low Level, Moderate Level, High Level and Very High Level, respectively. There were six (6) questions for the respondents to answer in each area of leadership skills such as, administrative skills, interpersonal skills and conceptual skills; and, five (5) questions in each area of supervisory skills such as, quality assurance, technical assistance and monitoring and evaluation.

Validity of the research instruments

An instrument is valid if it is able to measure what it is supposed to measure (Johnson and Kuby 2013). Moreover, Pagano (2011) explained that an instrument is considered valid if its purpose for which it is designed is met.

Hence, the research instruments were subjected to face and content validation following the criteria set by Good and Scates by presenting the instruments to five (5) experts in the field of research and educational management. One of the juries was the chief of Curriculum Implementation Division of the Division of Bacolod City and the four (4) other juries were currently the Public Schools District Supervisors in the Department of Education, Division of Bacolod City who are all holders of doctorate degree in educational management. Their suggestions and recommendations were incorporated in the final reproduction of the research instrument.

The validity status reached a rating of 4.76 for both the school heads and teachers, interpreted as "very good."

Reliability of the research instruments

An instrument is said to be reliable when it yields the same or identical results even if conducted twice (Pagano 2011). Thus, reliability of the instruments was established using the Cronbach Alpha administered to thirty (30) teachers and thirty (30) school heads in the Division of Negros Occidental as dry run respondents.

For school heads, the computed alpha for leadership skills was 0.958 interpreted as "very high reliable" and supervisory skills was 0.964 interpreted as "very high reliable". When taken altogether, the computed alpha was 0.975 interpreted as "very high reliable".

For teachers, the computed alpha for leadership skills was 0.986 interpreted as "very high reliable" and supervisory skills was 0.980 interpreted as "very high reliable". When taken altogether, the computed alpha was 0.989 interpreted as "very high reliable".

Data-gathering Procedures

To gather data that were used for the study, the researcher sought the permission of the Schools Division Superintendent of the Division of Bacolod City to conduct the said study. After the official permission was obtained, reliability testing then was administered to determine the reliability of the research instrument. Then, administration of the questionnaires to the respondents followed with the assistance of Public Schools District Supervisors of each of the seven districts of the division.

Distribution of the test questionnaires was done after the approval of all the seven district supervisors who were stationed in their offices at the DepEd Sub-Regional office beside the Division of Bacolod City office.

During the administration of test questionnaires, the researcher went on a school-to-school to gather the data needed for the study and conducted a short briefing to the respondents before the proper administration of the questionnaires for better understanding of the nature of study. Likewise, the researcher clarified issues and concerns that were raised concerning the items on the test questionnaire.

After questionnaires were collected, they were carefully tallied, and subjected to analyses and interpretation employing appropriate analytical schemes and statistical tools.

Analytical Schemes

For problem no. 1 which was to find out the profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, length of service as teacher or school head and highest educational attainment, the descriptive analytical scheme was used.

For problem no. 2 was to find out the level of school heads' leadership skills as assessed by teachers and by themselves in terms of administrative skills, interpersonal skills and conceptual skills, the descriptive analytical scheme was used.

For problem no. 3 was to find out the level of school heads' supervisory skills as assessed by teachers and by themselves in terms of quality assurance, technical assistance and monitoring and evaluation, the descriptive analytical scheme was used.

For problem no. 4 was to find out the level of teachers' performance in terms of teaching-learning process, learners' outcome and community involvement, the descriptive analytical scheme was used.

For problem no. 5 which was to find out the level of school heads' leadership skills as assessed by teachers and by themselves when they are grouped according to the aforementioned variables, the descriptive analytical scheme was likewise used.

For problem no. 6 which was to find out the level of school heads' supervisory skills as assessed by teachers and by themselves when they are grouped according to the aforementioned variables, the descriptive analytical scheme was likewise used.

For problem no. 7 which was to find out the level of teachers' performance when they are grouped according to the aforementioned variables, the descriptive analytical scheme was likewise used.

For problem no. 8 which was to find out whether or not significant difference exists in the level of school heads' leadership skills when grouped and compared according to aforementioned variables, the comparative analytical scheme was utilized.

For problem no. 9 which was to find out whether or not significant difference exists in the level of school heads' supervisory skills when grouped and compared according to aforementioned variables, the comparative analytical scheme was utilized.

For problem no. 10 which was to find out whether or not significant difference exists in the level of teachers' performance when grouped and compared according to aforementioned variables, the comparative analytical scheme was utilized.

For problem no. 11 which was to find out whether or not significant relationship exists between the level of school heads' leadership skills and level of teachers' performance, the relational analytical scheme was used.

For problem no. 12 which was to find out whether or not significant relationship exists between the level of school heads' supervisory skills and level of teachers' performance, the relational analytical scheme was used.

Statistical Tools

The researcher carefully selected appropriate statistical tools that were employed to each specific problem. Selection of statistical tools was based from the nature of problems that were formulated.

For problem no. 1 which was to find out the profile of the respondents in terms of the selected variables, the frequency and percentage scoring were used.

For problem no. 2 which was to find out the level of school heads' leadership skills as assessed by teachers and by themselves in terms of selected areas, the mean was employed. Johnson and Kuby (2013) explained that the mean is the most appropriate tool to measure the central tendency of an object of measure.

To measure the level of school heads' leadership skills the following was used:

Mean scoring	Verbal Interpretation
4.24 – 5.04	Very High Level
3.43 – 4.23	High Level
2.62 – 3.42	Moderate Level
1.81 – 2.61	Low Level
1.00 – 1.80	Very Low Level

For problem no. 3 which was to find out the level of school heads' supervisory skills as assessed by teachers and by themselves in terms of selected areas, the mean was also employed.

To measure the level of school heads' supervisory skills the following was used:

Mean scoring	Verbal Interpretation
4.24 – 5.04	Very High Level
3.43 – 4.23	High Level
2.62 – 3.42	Moderate Level
1.81 – 2.61	Low Level
1.00 – 1.80	Very Low Level

For problem no. 4 which was to find out the level of teachers' performance in terms of selected areas, the mean was again employed.

To measure the level of teachers' performance the following was used:

Mean scoring	Verbal Interpretation
4.500 – 5.000	Outstanding
3.500 – 4.499	Very Satisfactory
2.500 – 3.499	Satisfactory
1.500 – 2.499	Unsatisfactory
1.000 – 1.499	Poor

For problem no. 5 which was to find out the level of school heads' leadership skills as assessed by teachers and by themselves when they were grouped according to the aforementioned variables, the mean for grouped scores was used. Johnson and Kuby (2013) explained that the mean is the most appropriate tool to measure the central tendency of an object of measure.

For problem no. 6 which was to find out the level of school heads' supervisory skills as assessed by teachers and by themselves when they were grouped according to the aforementioned variables, the mean for grouped scores was also used.

For problem no. 7 which was to find out the level of teachers' performance when they were grouped according to the aforementioned variables, the mean for grouped scores was again used.

For problem no. 8 which was to find out whether or not significant difference exists in the level of school heads' leadership skills when grouped and compared according to aforementioned variables, the z-test was used. According to Bluman (2014) z-test is appropriate for measuring the significant difference between the two groups. Pagano (2011) added that it can be used when the study requires comparison of groups on the basis of certain variables.

The 0.05 level of significance was used as a basis for accepting or rejecting the null hypothesis. If the p-value is greater than 0.05 level of significance, accept the null hypothesis. If the p-value is less than or equal to 0.05 level of significance, reject the null hypothesis, Bluman (2014).

For problem no. 9 which was to find out whether or not significant difference exists in the level of school heads' supervisory skills when grouped and compared according to aforementioned variables, the z-test was also used.

For problem no. 10 which was to find out whether or not significant difference exists in the level of teachers' performance when grouped and compared according to aforementioned variables, the z-test was again used.

For problem no. 11 which was to find out whether or not significant relationship exists between the level of school heads' leadership skills and level of teachers' performance, the Pearson Product Moment of Correlation or Pearson r was used. Bluman (2014) clarifies that Pearson Product Moment of Correlation or Pearson r is appropriate for measuring the relationship of an interval or ratio type of variables.

To measure the significant relationship in accepting or rejecting the null hypothesis, if the p-value is greater than 0.05 level of significance, accept the null hypothesis. If the p-value is less than or equal to 0.05 level of significance, reject the null hypothesis.

For problem no. 12 which was to find out whether or not significant relationship exists between the level of school heads' supervisory skills and level of teachers' performance, the Pearson Product Moment of Correlation or Pearson r was also used.

Findings and Discussion:

Table 2
Profile of Teacher Respondents in Terms of Variables Used in this Study

Variable Grouping	Classification	Frequency	Percent
Age	Younger (below 42 years old)	163	49.4
	Older (42 years old and above)	167	50.6
	Total	330	100
Sex	Male	37	11.2
	Female	293	88.8
	Total	330	100
Length of Service as Teacher	Shorter (below 14 years)	152	46.1
	Longer (14 years and above)	178	53.9
	Total	330	100
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower (finished bachelor's degree)	221	67
	Higher (master's degree units and other graduate or post-graduate studies)	109	33
	Total	330	100

Statistics in Table 2 shows the total number of teachers as respondents of the study counted for 330. Age of teacher respondents was categorized into younger and older. To determine the demarcation line between younger and older, median was used which is 42 years old. Respondents below 42 years old were categorized as younger and 42 years old and above were categorized as older. There were 163 or 49.4% teacher respondents belong to the younger category and 167 or 50.6% belong to the older category. Greater number of teacher respondents belong to the older category than younger category.

As to sex, of the 330 teacher respondents, there were 37 or 11.2% of them belong to male and 293 or 88.8% belong to female. There were lesser number of male respondents than female.

As to length of service as teachers, it was categorized as shorter and longer for which median was also used. The median for the length of service as teacher was 14 years. Length of service as teacher below 14 years was categorized as shorter and 14 years and above was categorized as longer. There were 152 or 46.1% belong to teacher respondents with shorter length of service and 178 or 53.9% belong to longer length of service. Number of teacher respondents with longer length of service were greater than teacher respondents who belong to shorter length of service.

As to highest educational attainment, it was categorized as lower and higher. Teacher respondents who had just finished their bachelor's degree were categorized as lower and those who had master's degree units and other graduate or post-graduate studies were categorized as higher. Of the total number of teacher respondents, there were 221 or 67% of them with lower category in the highest educational attainment and 109 or 33% with higher category in highest educational attainment. Greater number of teacher respondents were having lower category in highest educational attainment and less were having higher category in highest educational attainment.

Table 3

Profile of School Head Respondents in Terms of Variables Used in this Study

Variable Grouping	Classification	Frequency	Percent
Age	Younger (below 49 years old)	23	50.0
	Older (49 years old and above)	23	50.0
	Total	46	100
Sex	Male	13	28.3
	Female	33	71.7
	Total	46	100
Length of Service as School Head	Shorter (below 7 years)	20	43.5
	Longer (7 years and above)	26	56.5
	Total	46	100
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower (with master's degree units)	20	43.5
	Higher (finished master's degree and other post-graduate studies)	26	56.5
	Total	46	100

Statistics in Table 3 shows the total number of school heads as respondents of the study counted for 46. Age of school head respondents was categorized into younger and older. To determine the demarcation line between younger and older, median was used which is 49 years old. Respondents below 49 years old were categorized as younger and 49 years old and above were categorized as older. There were 23 or 50% school head respondents belong to both younger and older category. There were equal number of respondents to both younger and older category. As to sex, of the 46 school head respondents, there were 13 or 28.3% of them belong to male and 33 or 71.7% belong to female. There were lesser number of male respondents than female.

As to length of service as school head, it was categorized as shorter and longer for which median was also used. The median for the length of service as school head was 7 years. Length of service as school head below 7 years was categorized as shorter and 7 years and above was categorized as longer. There were 20 or 43.5% of school head respondents belong to shorter length of service and 26 or 56.5% belong to longer length of service. School head respondents belong to shorter length of service are lesser compared to those who belong to longer length of service.

As to highest educational attainment, it was categorized as lower and higher. School head respondents with master's degree units were categorized as lower and those who had finished master's degree and other post-graduate studies were categorized as higher. Of the total number of school head respondents, there were 20 or 43.5% of them with lower category in highest educational attainment and 26 or 56.5% with higher category in highest educational attainment. Greater number of school head respondents were having higher category in highest educational attainment and less were having lower category in highest educational attainment.

Table 4
Level of School Heads' Leadership Skills as Assessed by Teachers in Terms of the Aforementioned Areas

Area		Mean	Interpretation
Administrative Skills			
My school head...			
1	is effective with the detailed aspects of his/her work.	4.45	Very High Level
2	enjoys responding to people's requests and concerns.	4.37	Very High Level
3	has the ability to lead and implement educational programs.	4.48	Very High Level
4	has the ability to promote and coordinate services for holistic development of school personnel and pupils.	4.43	Very High Level
5	has the ability to determine the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats of the school.	4.41	Very High Level
6	has the ability to direct, coordinate and manage school funds according to prioritized needs.	4.44	Very High Level
Overall Mean		4.4288	Very High Level

Interpersonal Skills			
My school head...			
1	usually knows ahead of time how people will respond to a new idea or proposal.	4.29	Very High Level
2	has a good rapport/linkage with internal and external stakeholders.	4.37	Very High Level
3	is able to sense the emotional undercurrents in our group.	4.27	Very High Level
4	uses his/her emotional energy to motivate others.	4.33	Very High Level
5	interacts appropriately with a variety of audiences.	4.34	Very High Level
6	finds it easy to solve conflicts.	4.25	Very High Level
Overall Mean		4.3101	Very High Level
Conceptual Skills			
My school head...			
1	is effective at problem solving.	4.30	Very High Level
2	skillfully makes strategic plans for our organization.	4.38	Very High Level
3	enjoys discussing organizational values and philosophy.	4.41	Very High Level
4	is flexible about making changes in our organization.	4.39	Very High Level
5	has the ability to make intervention/innovation for learners' development.	4.40	Very High Level
6	has the ability to mediate and ensure resolution of conflicts in school.	4.32	Very High Level
Overall Mean		4.3684	Very High Level

Statistics in table 4 shows the level of school heads' leadership skills as assessed by teachers in the areas of administrative skills, interpersonal skills and conceptual skills. These were obtained using the approved survey questionnaires stated in the point of view of the teachers with 6 questions in each of the area answered by the 330 teacher respondents.

In the area of administrative skills, the highest mean score was 4.48 interpreted as "Very High Level" on the issue of "My school head has the ability to lead and implement educational programs." On the other hand, the lowest mean score was 4.37 interpreted as "Very High Level" on the issue of "My school head enjoys responding to people's requests and concerns." The overall mean score for administrative skills was 4.4288 interpreted as "Very High Level". In the area of interpersonal skills, the highest mean score was 4.37 interpreted as "Very High Level" on the issue of "My school head has a good rapport/linkage with internal and external stakeholders." On the other hand, the lowest mean score was 4.25 interpreted as "Very High Level" on the issue of "My school head finds it easy to solve conflicts." The overall mean score for interpersonal skills was 4.3101 interpreted as "Very High Level".

In the area of conceptual skills, the highest mean score was 4.41 interpreted as "Very High Level" on the issue of "My school head enjoys discussing organizational values and philosophy." On the other hand, the lowest mean score was 4.30 interpreted as "Very High Level" on the issue of "My school head is effective at problem solving." The overall mean score for conceptual skills was 4.3684 interpreted as "Very High Level".

In the areas of school heads' leadership skills when assessed by teachers the highest mean score was 4.4288 interpreted as "Very High Level" on the issue of administrative skills and the lowest mean score was 4.3101 interpreted as "Very High Level" on the issue of interpersonal skills.

Table 4 shows the level of school heads' leadership skills as assessed by teachers in terms of the aforementioned areas.

Table 5**Level of School Heads' Leadership Skills as Assessed by Themselves in Terms of the Aforementioned Areas**

Area		Mean	Interpretation
Administrative Skills			
1	I am effective with the detailed aspects of my work.	4.28	Very High Level
2	In my work, I enjoy responding to people's requests and concerns.	4.63	Very High Level
3	I have the ability to lead and implement educational programs.	4.59	Very High Level
4	I have the ability to promote and coordinate services for holistic development of school personnel and pupils.	4.54	Very High Level
5	I have the ability to determine the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats of the school.	4.46	Very High Level
6	I have the ability to direct, coordinate and manage	4.61	Very High Level

	school funds according to prioritized needs.		
Overall Mean		4.5174	Very High Level
Interpersonal Skills			
1	I usually know ahead of time how people will respond to a new idea or proposal.	4.04	High Level
2	I have a good rapport/linkage with internal and external stakeholders.	4.35	Very High Level
3	I am able to sense the emotional undercurrents in my group.	4.28	Very High Level
4	I use my emotional energy to motivate others.	4.28	Very High Level
5	I interact appropriately with a variety of audiences.	4.52	Very High Level
6	I find it easy to solve conflicts.	4.09	High Level
Overall Mean		4.2609	Very High Level
Conceptual Skills			
1	I am effective at problem solving.	4.13	High Level
2	I skillfully make strategic plans for my organization.	4.11	High Level
3	I enjoy discussing organizational values and philosophy.	4.43	Very High Level
4	I am flexible about making changes in our organization.	4.50	Very High Level
5	I have the ability to make intervention/innovation for learners' development.	4.22	High Level
6	I have the ability to mediate and ensure resolution of conflicts in school.	4.35	Very High Level
Overall Mean		4.2900	Very High Level

Statistics in table 5 shows the level of school heads' leadership skills as assessed by themselves in the areas of administrative skills, interpersonal skills and conceptual skills. These were obtained using the approved survey questionnaire stated in the point of view of the school heads with 6 questions in each of the area answered by the 46 school head respondents.

In the area of administrative skills, the highest mean score was 4.63 interpreted as "Very High Level" on the issue of "In my work, I enjoy responding to people's requests and concerns." On the other hand, the lowest mean score was 4.28 interpreted as "Very High Level" on the issue of "I am effective with the detailed aspects of my work." The overall mean score for administrative skills was 4.5174 interpreted as "Very High Level".

In the area of interpersonal skills, the highest mean score was 4.52 interpreted as "Very High Level" on the issue of "I interact appropriately with a variety of audiences." On the other hand, the lowest mean score was 4.04 interpreted as "Very High Level" on the issue of "I usually know ahead of time how people will respond to a new idea or proposal." The overall mean score for interpersonal skills was 4.2609 interpreted as "Very High Level".

In the area of conceptual skills, the highest mean score was 4.50 interpreted as "Very High Level" on the issue of "I am flexible about making changes in our organization." On the other hand, the lowest mean score was 4.11 interpreted as "Very High Level" on the issue of "I skillfully make strategic plans for my organization." The overall mean score for conceptual skills was 4.2900 interpreted as "Very High Level".

In the areas of school heads' leadership skills when assessed by themselves the highest mean score was 4.5174 interpreted as "Very High Level" on the issue of administrative skills and the lowest mean score was 4.2609 interpreted as "Very High Level" on the issue of interpersonal skills.

Table 6
Level of School Heads' Supervisory Skills as Assessed by Teachers in Terms of the Aforementioned Areas

Area		Mean	Interpretation
Quality Assurance			
My school head...			
1	is aware of all the indicators/areas for instructional supervision.	4.51	Very High Level
2	knows the goals and objectives of instructional supervision.	4.56	Very High Level
3	prepares instructional supervision plan that shows the prescribed standard process for instructional supervision.	4.53	Very High Level
4	has strategies that address the specific needs of teachers of the school.	4.45	Very High Level
5	based his/her ISP strategies on sound pedagogy.	4.49	Very High Level
Overall Mean		4.5091	Very High Level
Technical Assistance			

My school head...			
1	conducts need assessment of teachers as basis for his/her Technical Assistance (TA) plan.	4.52	Very High Level
2	prepares Technical Assistance (TA) plan to include the performance targets set by him/her and the teachers.	4.51	Very High Level
3	periodically monitors the teachers' implementation of our agreed strategies.	4.52	Very High Level
4	analyzes and consolidates the findings on the implementation of the TA plan and provide feedback to teachers.	4.49	Very High Level
5	has an overall assessment of the implementation of his/her TA plan.	4.52	Very High Level
Overall Mean		4.5145	Very High Level
Monitoring and Evaluation			
My school head...			
1	has a monitoring plan to assess the implementation of the technical assistance among the teachers of the school.	4.53	Very High Level
2	prepares an orientation meeting among teachers to clarify how they are to be assessed based on the monitoring plan.	4.54	Very High Level
3	conducts progress monitoring among the teachers.	4.52	Very High Level
4	analyzes and consolidates the findings of his/her monitoring and provide feedback to teachers.	4.49	Very High Level
5	has an overall assessment of the progress of his/her teachers.	4.53	Very High Level
Overall Mean		4.5218	Very High Level

Statistics in table 6 shows the level of school heads' supervisory skills as assessed by teachers in the areas of quality assurance, technical assistance and monitoring and evaluation. These were obtained using the approved survey questionnaire stated in the point of view of the teachers with 5 questions in each of the area answered by the 330 teacher respondents.

In the area of quality assurance, the highest mean score was 4.56 interpreted as "Very High Level" on the issue of "My school head knows the goals and objectives of instructional supervision." On the other hand, the lowest mean score was 4.45 interpreted as "Very High Level" on the issue of "My school head has strategies that address the specific needs of teachers of the school." The overall mean score for quality assurance was 4.5091 interpreted as "Very High Level".

In the area of technical assistance, the highest mean score was 4.52 interpreted as "Very High Level" on the issues of "My school head conducts need assessment of teachers as basis for his/her Technical Assistance (TA) plan," "My school head periodically monitors the teachers' implementation of our agreed strategies," and "My school head has an overall assessment of the implementation of his/her TA plan." On the other hand, the lowest mean score was 4.49 interpreted as "Very High Level" on the issue of "My school head analyzes and consolidates the findings on the implementation of the TA plan and provide feedback to teachers." The overall mean score for technical assistance was 4.5145 interpreted as "Very High Level".

In the area of monitoring and evaluation, the highest mean score was 4.54 interpreted as "Very High Level" on the issue of "My school head prepares an orientation meeting among teachers to clarify how they are to be assessed based on the monitoring plan." On the other hand, the lowest mean score was 4.49 interpreted as "Very High Level" on the issue of "My school head analyzes and consolidates the findings of his/her monitoring and provide feedback to teachers." The overall mean score for monitoring and evaluation was 4.5218 interpreted as "Very High Level".

In the areas of school heads' supervisory skills when assessed by teachers the highest mean score was 4.5218 interpreted as "Very High Level" on the issue of monitoring and evaluation, and the lowest mean score was 4.5091 interpreted as "Very High Level" on the issue of quality assurance.

Table 7
Level of School Heads' Supervisory Skills as Assessed by Themselves in Terms of the Aforementioned Areas

Area		Mean	Interpretation
Quality Assurance			
1	I am aware of all the indicators/areas for instructional supervision.	4.54	Very High Level
2	I know the goals and objectives of instructional	4.67	Very High Level

	supervision.		
3	My Instructional Supervision plan shows the prescribed standard process for instructional supervision.	4.48	Very High Level
4	My ISP has strategies that address the specific needs of teachers of the school.	4.41	Very High Level
5	I based my ISP strategies on sound pedagogy.	4.39	Very High Level
Overall Mean		4.5000	Very High Level
Technical Assistance			
1	I conducted needs assessment of teachers as basis for my Technical Assistance (TA) plan.	4.28	Very High Level
2	I prepared a Technical Assistance (TA) plan to include the performance targets set by me and the teachers.	4.22	High Level
3	I periodically monitored the teachers' implementation of our agreed strategies.	4.07	High Level
4	I analyzed and consolidated the findings on the implementation of the TA plan and provide feedback to teachers.	4.26	Very High Level
5	I have an overall assessment of the implementation of my TA plan.	4.13	High Level
Overall Mean		4.1913	High Level
Monitoring and Evaluation			
1	I have a monitoring plan to assess the implementation of the technical assistance among the teachers of the school.	4.09	High Level
2	I prepared an orientation meeting among teachers to clarify how they are to be assessed based on the monitoring plan.	4.24	Very High Level
3	I conducted progress monitoring among the teachers.	4.13	High Level
4	I analyzed and consolidated the findings of my monitoring and provide feedback to teachers.	4.13	High Level
5	I have an overall assessment of the progress of my teachers.	4.20	High Level
Overall Mean		4.1565	High Level

Statistics in table 7 shows the level of school heads' supervisory skills as assessed by themselves in the areas of quality assurance, technical assistance and monitoring and evaluation. These were obtained using the approved survey questionnaire stated in the point of view of the school heads with 5 questions in each of the area answered by the 46 school head respondents.

In the area of quality assurance, the highest mean score was 4.67 interpreted as "Very High Level" on the issue of "I know the goals and objectives of instructional supervision." On the other hand, the lowest mean score was 4.39 interpreted as "Very High Level" on the issue of "I based my ISP strategies on sound pedagogy." The overall mean score for quality assurance was 4.5000 interpreted as "Very High Level".

In the area of technical assistance, the highest mean score was 4.28 interpreted as "Very High Level" on the issue of "I conducted needs assessment of teachers as basis for my Technical Assistance (TA) plan." On the other hand, the lowest mean score was 4.07 interpreted as "High Level" on the issue of "I periodically monitored the teachers' implementation of our agreed strategies." The overall mean score for technical assistance was 4.1913 interpreted as "High Level".

In the area of monitoring and evaluation, the highest mean score was 4.24 interpreted as "Very High Level" on the issue of "I prepared an orientation meeting among teachers to clarify how they are to be assessed based on the monitoring plan." On the other hand, the lowest mean score was 4.09 interpreted as "High Level" on the issue of "I have a monitoring plan to assess the implementation of the technical assistance among the teachers of the school." The overall mean score for monitoring and evaluation was 4.1565 interpreted as "High Level".

In the areas of school heads' supervisory skills when assessed by themselves the highest mean score was 4.5000 interpreted as "Very High Level" on the issue of quality assurance and the lowest mean score was 4.1565 interpreted as "High Level" on the issue of monitoring and evaluation.

Conclusions:

Based on the foregoing findings of the study, the conclusions that were derived were as follows:

On the profile of teacher respondents, this proved that the work in the Department of Education is dominated by females as represented by 88.8% female teacher respondents and that only 11.2% are males. Most of the teachers

belonged to the lower category in highest educational attainment (finished bachelor's degree) probably because they focused most of their time in their work as classroom teacher. And that, it cannot be denied that teachers' first thing to do after landing in a job is to support their families. Most of the teachers fell on prey to lending institutions to finance the study of their siblings, repair of homes and sending members of the family to medical cares. Thus, depriving them in taking further studies for their personal and professional growth and development.

On the profile of school head respondents, where the age categorization is 49 years old, this proved that before these teachers were promoted as school heads, they had already gained enough experience as classroom teachers and that from among the candidates for promotion where most of them were females, the tendency is, even in school heads, greater number of them were females. Having promoted in later age, the median length of service as school heads was only 7 years. As a result of the city's scholarship grants through PESO, through the effort of BCPSTF, greater number of school heads were having higher category in highest educational attainment. These enabled the school heads being enrolled and finished graduate studies and even post-graduate studies where in the researcher is one of them.

On the level of school heads' leadership skills when assessed by teachers and by themselves in the aforementioned areas, where in all of the areas were interpreted as "Very High Level", both teachers and school heads evaluated interpersonal skills as the lowest, more particularly on the issues of "My school head finds it easy to solve conflicts" on teachers' perspective and "I usually know ahead of time how people will respond to a new idea or proposal" on the school heads' perspective. These proved that seminars and trainings conducted by the division office were effective on the development of administrative skills and conceptual skills of school heads while the development of interpersonal skills were least effective. One of the American soldiers have said, "The best way to capture the nation is to subjugate the hearts and minds of the people." On this case, we cannot just simply say, "Follow what I say but do not follow what I do." Still, modelling works better than saying.

On the level of school heads' supervisory skills, teachers and school heads had a contrasting evaluation on the area of quality assurance where teachers scored it as the lowest and school heads scored the highest. On the area of monitoring and evaluation, teachers scored this as the highest and school heads evaluated this otherwise. Contrasting perception of teachers and school heads on these two areas spoke about the contrasting interest between teachers and school heads. Teachers viewed quality assurance as the least area that school heads were exercising most especially on the issue of "My school head has strategies that address the specific needs of teachers of the school" proved that school heads might have applied one strategy to all teachers. In dealing with diverse teachers, school heads should have applied diverse strategy also which means that one strategy may or may not be applicable to all teachers. On the part of school heads where monitoring and evaluation was viewed as their weakest but evaluated by teachers as the strongest, proved that the planned activities were not properly executed. School heads failed to comply with the issue on "I have a monitoring plan to assess the implementation of the technical assistance among the teachers of the school" for the improvement of teachers' performance. In this instance, the saying, "Failed to plan is planning to fail" is very evident.

On the level of teachers' performance, where all areas were interpreted as "Very Satisfactory", community involvement scored the lowest. It can be concluded that teachers focused on the teaching-learning process and learners' outcome while community involvement was left behind. This justifies now deficiency of school heads on interpersonal relationships. Where school heads are more particular on administrative skills and conceptual skills and viewed by teachers that they devote their time more on monitoring and evaluation, most likely the result will be on teaching-learning process and learners' outcome. As an old African Proverb said, "It takes a village to raise a child," failure on the part of the school to involve other players in education will result to difficulty on producing quality learners, taking into account that learners' outcome fell next to community involvement. Trainings and seminars which were effective on administrative skills and conceptual skills must be balanced by the development of interpersonal skills.

On the level of school heads' leadership skills as assessed by teachers when they were grouped according to sex, wherein male group assessed school heads "High Level" in all of the areas especially on the issue of "My school head enjoys responding to people's requests and concerns" scored lowest by male group in administrative skills can be concluded that, for male teachers, school heads did not enjoy responding to people's requests and concerns. They might had forgotten that they were the reason why we were in school and that they were our business. We can further conclude that, this was one effect of poor interpersonal skills and probably, Citizen's Charter as mandated, was not working well in schools to serve better the clients. On the issue of "My school head is able to sense the emotional undercurrents in our group" scored lowest by males in interpersonal skills can be concluded that, for male teachers, school heads were just passive and not sensitive to the emotions of teachers. These acts would lead the teachers to external completion and internal rebellion most especially by male teachers. On the issue of "My school head is effective at problem solving" scored lowest by both sexes in conceptual skills was a manifestation that school heads, generally, poor at resolving conflicts in schools and might be, in some cases, the source of conflicts.

On the level of school heads' leadership skills as assessed by themselves when they were grouped according to age, length of service as school head and highest educational attainment in the area of interpersonal skills on the issue of "I

usually know ahead of time how people will respond to a new idea or proposal" was rated lowest by the younger group, both shorter and longer group and lower group, respectively. In this case, we can probably say that, for them, they lack anticipation on the reactions of people to a new idea or proposals. Newton's Third Law of Motion, "In every action, there is an equal and opposite reaction." They should have to be always prepared to reactions of people especially that of the antagonists and pessimists. On the issue of "I skillfully make strategic plans for my organization" in the area of conceptual skills where both younger and older groups scored the lowest, we can conclude that, strategic planning is one skill that they should possess to address specific needs and problems of schools. On the same issue, when grouped according to sex, both males and females gave the lowest score on the same area.

On the level of school heads' supervisory skills as assessed by teachers when they were grouped according to sex, length of service as teacher and highest educational attainment in the area of quality assurance on the issue of "My school head has strategies that address the specific needs of teachers of the school" where both groups and younger group evaluated the lowest can be concluded that, for teachers, strategies that were used by school heads did not address the specific needs of teachers and that specific problems were not solved. In the area of technical assistance on the issue of "My school head analyzes and consolidates the findings on the implementation of the TA plan and provide feedback to teachers" where older group, both sexes, longer group and lower group in highest educational attainment evaluated the lowest can be concluded that feedbacking was not given importance. The same is true in the area of monitoring and evaluation on the issue of "My school head analyzes and consolidates the findings of his/her monitoring and provide feedback to teachers. When grouped according to age, sex and highest educational attainment in the area of monitoring and evaluation on the issue of "My school head analyzes and consolidates the findings of his/her monitoring and provide feedback to teachers" where both groups and shorter length of service as teacher evaluated school heads the lowest can be concluded that, generally, for teachers, school heads forgot to analyze and consolidate the findings of his/her monitoring and probably did not provide feedback to them. Feedback is important to gather valuable information that will be used to make important decisions. This is important to teachers to make their best even better. Effective feedback has benefits for the giver, the receiver and the wider organization.

On the level of school heads' supervisory skills as assessed by themselves when they were grouped according to sex and length of service as school head in the area of quality assurance on the issue of "I based my ISP strategies on sound pedagogy" where both groups, older group and lower group in highest educational attainment evaluated themselves the lowest can be concluded that, Instructional Supervision Plans were not based on the required skills and knowledge teachers need in order to be effective. When grouped according age, sex, length of service as school head and highest educational attainment in the area of technical assistance on the issue of "I periodically monitored the teachers' implementation of our agreed strategies" where all groups evaluated themselves the lowest can be concluded that, monitoring on the agreed strategies were not implemented. And that, none if not less technical assistance were given to teachers to improve their performance. In the area of monitoring and evaluation on the issue of "I have a monitoring plan to assess the implementation of technical assistance among the teachers of the school" where one group or the other if not both evaluated themselves the lowest supports the findings in the area of technical assistance where less TA were given to teachers. And that, there was an absence of technical assistance much more on monitoring and evaluation.

On the level of teachers' performance when they were grouped according to age, sex and length of service as teacher where teachers performed least in the area of community involvement can be concluded that, teachers did not give so much value on community involvement in education. They did not realize the importance of community involvement most especially in physical improvement of the school. When school, parents, families and communities work together to support learning, learners tend to earn higher grades, attend school more regularly, stay in school longer and enroll in higher level programs.

On the difference in the level of school heads' leadership skills when grouped and compared according to aforementioned variables in all areas, where null hypotheses were accepted, we can conclude that, school heads' leadership skills in all areas had no significant difference when grouped and compared according to aforementioned variables. This means that school heads' leadership skills for one group had no significant difference with that of the other group.

On the difference in the level of school heads' supervisory skills when grouped and compared according to aforementioned variables in all areas, where null hypotheses were accepted, we can conclude that, school heads' leadership skills in all areas had no significant difference when grouped and compared according to aforementioned variables. This means that school heads' leadership skills for one group had no significant difference with that of the other group.

On the difference in the level of teachers' performance in the area of teaching-learning process when grouped and compared according to age, sex and length of service as teacher, where null hypotheses were rejected, we can conclude that, there were significant differences in the level of teachers' performance in the area of teaching-learning process when grouped and compared according to the earlier mentioned variables and that performance of one group differs that of the other group. We can conclude further that, older group performed better than the younger group,

females performed better than males and longer in the length of service performed better than shorter in the length of service.

When grouped and compared according to highest educational attainment, where null hypothesis was accepted, we can conclude that there was no significant difference in the level of performance of lower group than that of the higher group in highest educational attainment. On the difference in the level of teachers' performance in the area of learners' outcome when grouped and compared according to age, sex and highest educational attainment, where null hypotheses were accepted, we can conclude that, there were no significant differences in the level of teachers' performance in the area of learners' outcome when grouped and compared according to the earlier mentioned variables and that performance of one group did not differ that of the other group. When grouped and compared according to length of service as teacher, where null hypothesis was rejected, we can conclude that, there was a significant difference in the level of teachers' performance in the area of learners' outcome when grouped and compared according to length of service as teacher and that performance of one group differs that of the other group. We can conclude further that, those who served longer as teacher performed better than the shorter ones.

On the difference in the level of teachers' performance in the area of community involvement when grouped and compared according to age and length of service as teacher, where null hypotheses were accepted, we can conclude that, there were no significant differences in the level of teachers' performance in the area of community involvement when grouped and compared according to the earlier mentioned variables and that performance of one group did not differ that of the other group. When grouped and compared according to sex and highest educational attainment, where null hypotheses were rejected, we can conclude that, there were significant differences in the level of teachers' performance in the area of community involvement when grouped and compared according to earlier mentioned variables and that performance of one group differs that of the other group. We can conclude further that, females performed better than males and those who are in higher group in highest educational attainment performed better than the lower group.

On relationship between the level of school heads' leadership skills and the level of teachers' performance, where null hypothesis was accepted, we can conclude that, there was no significant relationship between the level of school heads' leadership skills and the level of teachers' performance and that level of school heads' leadership skills did not influence the level of teachers' performance.

On relationship between the level of school heads' supervisory skills and the level of teachers' performance, where null hypothesis was rejected, we can conclude that, there was a significant relationship between the level of school heads' supervisory skills and the level of teachers' performance and that level of school heads' supervisory skills significantly influenced the level of teachers' performance. We can conclude further that, improved supervisory skills results to improved teachers' performance.

References:

Adegbemile, Oluwadare, "Principals' Competency Needs for Effective Schools' Administration In Nigeria", (2011)

Ali, IS, "Principal Leadership Style and School Performance", (2013)

Aguilar, Elena, "What Makes a Great School Leader?", (2014)

Akerele, SA., "Principals Leadership Styles and Teachers' Job Performance in Lagos State Public Secondary Schools", (2013)

Aunga and Masare, "Effect of Leadership Styles on Teacher's Performance in Primary Schools of Arusha District Tanzania", (2017)

Azucena Jr, J. A., Geroso, M. J. S., & Maguate, G. S. (2023). Contingent Educational Management Response: The Construction and Validation of Leadership Scale in the Era of Change. *International Journal of Latest Research in Humanities and Social Science (IJLRHSS)*, 6(07). 315-327.

Barker, B., "Do Leaders Matter?", (2011)

Baroa, Enjennette D., "Adversity Quotient and Leadership Skills of School Administrators: Basis for Leadership Enhancement Program", (2015)

Bateh, J., Heyliger, W., "Academic Administrator Leadership Styles and the Impact on Faculty Job Satisfaction and Self-Esteem", (2014)

- Biggerstaff, J.K., "The Relationship Between Teacher Perceptions of Elementary School Principal Leadership Style and Teacher Job Satisfaction", (2012)
- Bolanle, Akinola, "Principals' Leadership Skills and School Effectiveness: The Case of South Western Nigeria", (2013)
- Bolei, "The Teachers' Perceptions of Headteachers' Human Skills Practice in Secondary School Management and How This Influences Their Work Commitment: The Case of Baringo District, Kenya", (2012)
- Callaghan, C.W., & Coldwell, D., "Job Satisfaction and Job Performance: The Case of Research Productivity", (2014)
- Canivel, L., "AQ and Leadership Style, Performance and Best Practices", (2010)
- Castaneda, Ana Marie B., "Leadership Skills of the School Heads", (2017)
- Clark, P.Y., "Teachers As Designers in Self-directed Learning", (2015)
- Craus, A., Geroso, P. J. M., & Maguate, G. (2023). Assessment of School Improvement Plan 2013-2015: Basis for the Technical Assistance Plan. Valley International Journal Digital Library, 2952-3035.
- Doyle, Allison, "Conceptual Skills List and Examples", (2018)
- Drew, G. & Ehrich, L.C., "A Model of Organizational Leadership Development Informing Succession Development: Elements and Practices", (2012)
- Dumagat, Mary Grace M., "Leadership Attitude and Competencies of Private Secondary School Administrators", (2011)
- Ekundayo, H.T., Oyerinde, D.O. & Kolawole, A.O., "Effective Supervision of Instruction in Nigerian Secondary Schools: Issues, Challenges and the Way Forward", (2013)
- Esmane, Danilo, "Leadership Disposition and Decision-Making Skills of Public School Administrator in Southern Negros: Basis for Enhanced Collaborative Professional Learning Communities", (2015)
- Esteron, Annie N., "Technical Assistance Mechanism and Schools' Performance in the Division of Bacolod City", (2014)
- Eya, P.E. & Leonard, C.C., "Effective Supervision of Instruction in Nigerian Secondary Schools: Issues in Quality Assurance", (2012)
- Eliver, A., Abule, A., Cornel, M., & Maguate, G. (2023). Teachers Research Perception, Competence and Work Performance: Basis for A Capability Building Plan. International Journal of Scientific Research and Management (IJSRM), 11(10), 42-73.
- Farah, Abdikadir Issa, "School Management: Characteristics of Effective Principal", (2013)
- Farhat, M. & Usman, K., "Secondary School Teachers' Perceptions of their Principals' Leadership Behaviors and their Academic Performance at Secondary School Level", (2016)
- Ferrer, M., "Relationship Of Personal Characteristics, Leadership Styles, And Job Satisfaction To Adversity Quotient Of Academic Heads Of Selected State Colleges And Universities In The National Capital Region", (2009)
- Fulgencio, R. G., & Maguate, G. S. Awareness and Implementation of the Public Elementary School Teachers of the Positive Discipline Model: Basis for a Guidance Program, (2023).
- Galang, Sarah A., "Organizational Culture, Leadership Competence and Performance of State Universities and Colleges", (2015)
- Gardner, H., "Fostering Diversity Through Personalized Education: Implications of a New Understanding of Human Intelligence", (1997)
- Gernalin, J., Bautista, M., & Maguate, G. (2023). Compliance with the code of Conduct and Teaching Performance. Valley International Journal Digital Library, 3036-3062.
- Geroso, P. J. M. S., & Maguate, G. (2023). Organizational, Social, Economic and Financial Management Performance of Cooperatives. International Journal of Scientific Research and Management (IJSRM), 11(10), 5263-5282.

- Gillies, E., "Positive Professional Relationships", (2012)
- Green, G.S. & Sherony, K. M., "Co-Worker Exchange: Relationships Between Co-Workers Leader-Member Exchange, Work Attitudes", (2012)
- Jayne, R., & Maguate, G. (2023). Issues and Concerns of Teachers towards Modular Distance Learning Approach. International Journal of Scientific Research and Management (IJSRM), 11(08), 2848-2857.
- Johnson, S.M., Kraft, M.A., & Papay, J.P., "How Context Matters in High-need Schools: The Effects of Teachers' Working Conditions on Their Professional Satisfaction and Their Students' Achievement", (2012)
- Kashagate, R., "Influence of Leadership Style on Teachers' Performance in Tanzania: The Case of Public Secondary Schools in Musoma Municipal Council", (2013)
- Kersty Hobson, Ruth Mayne, Jo Hamilton, "What is Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E)", (2013)
- Koech & Namusonge, "The Effect of Leadership Styles on Organizational Performance", (2012)
- Kroll, B., "Building Relationship with Hard-to-Reach People: Establishing Rapport with Drug-Misusing Parents and Their Children", (2011)
- Hackman, M.Z. & Johnson, C.E., "Leadership: A Communication Perspective", (2011)
- Hosseinpour, et.al, "Principal's Management Skills and Their Effectiveness in Karaj 4th District Primary School", (2014)
- Ifedili, Josephine, "Instructional Supervision and Quality Assurance in Schools in Nigeria", (2015)
- Ikegbusi, et.al, "The Impact of Supervision of Instruction on Teacher Effectiveness in Secondary Schools in Nigeria", (2016)
- Ikegbusi, N.G. & Iheanacho, R.C., "Factors Militating Against Effective Administration of Secondary Schools in Anambra State", (2016)
- Ikegbusi, N.G., "Towards Enhancing Staff Personnel Management in Secondary Schools in Anambra State", (2014)
- Kamete, Janeth, "The Influence of Headmaster's Managerial Skills on Effective School Management: A Case of Public Secondary Schools in Mbeya – Tanzania", (2014)
- McColl-Kennedy, J.R. & Anderson, R.D., "Impact of Leadership Style and Emotions on Subordinate Performance", (2012)
- Macapagong, E., Maguate, G., & Geroso, M. J. S. (2023). Living and Teaching Internationally: Teachers' Experiences, Prospects and Challenges. Valley International Journal Digital Library, 2882-2894.
- Mecgley, M.N., "A handbook for Effective Supervision", (2015)
- Memisoglu, Salih, "The Perception of Teachers About Management Skills of School Principals", (2015)
- Moises, R. D., & Maguate, G. S. School Learning Actional Celland Professional Development. (2023).
- Mudulia, Mabel, "The Impact of Head Teachers' Administrative Factors on Performance in Secondary School Science Subjects in Eldoret Municipality, Kenya Ambogo", (2012)
- Muraina, Monsuru Babatunde Alvan Ikoku, "Principals' Managerial Skills and Administrative Effectiveness in Secondary Schools in Oyo State, Nigeria", (2014)
- Napire, Jodel N., "Adversity Quotient and Leadership Style in Relation to the Demographic Profile of the Elementary School Principals in the Second Congressional District of Camarines Sur", (2013)
- Ndungu, et.al., "Influence of Monitoring and Evaluation by Principals on Effective Teaching and Learning in Public Secondary Schools in Githunguri District", (2015)
- Nwogbo, V.N. and Okeke, B.C., "Teachers' Discipline and Commitment to Duty : A Veritable Instrument for Academic Excellence", (2010)

- Odumeru, J.A., & Ogbonna, I.G., "Transformational vs. Transactional Leadership Theories: Evidence in Literature", (2013)
- Ofojebe, W.N., Chukwuma, E.T.C. & Onyekwe, E.C., "Role of Internal Supervision on Teaching/Learning Effectiveness in the Management of Public Secondary Education in Anambra State", (2016)
- Ogba, F.N. & Igu, N.C.N., "Realizing Quality Education in Nigeria: The need to Revitalize Secondary Education", (2014)
- Ogbo, R.N., "Effects of Modified Clinical Supervision Approach on Teacher Instructional Performance in Ebonyi State", (2015)
- Ogundele, Michael, Olarewaju, "Principals' Administrative Skills for Secondary Schools in Plateau State, Nigeria", (2015)
- Okobia, T.A., "Approaches to Supervision of Instruction, Education and Development", (2015)
- Olefero, Ngozika, A., "Principals' Administrative Skills and Proper Conduct of Examination Among Students in Uyo Education Zone of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria", (2017)
- Otieno, FAO, "The Roles of Monitoring and Evaluation in Projects", (2012)
- Oyedeji, N.B., "Supervision and Standard of Education in Nigerian Secondary Schools", (2012)
- Pasique, D. A., & Maguate, G. (2023). Challenges and Opportunities Among Educators in The Implementation of Continuing Professional development. *International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research (IJFMR)*, 5(4).
- Price, Heather E., "Principal-Teacher Relationships: Foregrounding the International Importance of Principals' Social Relationships for School Learning Climates", (2015)
- Price, H.E., "Principal-Teacher Interactions: How Affective Relationships Shape Principal and Teacher Attitudes", (2012)
- Roffey, S., "Developing Positive Relationship in Schools", (2012)
- Sias, P.M., "Organizing Relationships: Traditional and Emerging Perspectives on Workplace Relationship", (2012)
- Simmonds, J., "Relating and Relationships in Supervision: Supporting and Companionable or Dominant and Submissive?", (2012)
- Syarwani, A., "The Influence of Management Capabilities to the Effectiveness of School Implementation", (2012)
- Talimodao, Juvy S., "Principals' Leadership Practices, Teachers' Morale and Pupils' Performance in Public Elementary Schools in the Division of Bacolod City", (2015)
- Tiauzon, M. J., Moyani Jr, G., Bautista, M., & Maguate, G. (2023). Management Skills of Department Heads in Relation to Employees Work Performance. *Valley International Journal Digital Library*, 5327-5334.
- Vishwanath, B., "Role of a Teacher in 21st Century", (2012)
- Walker, J.W., "Supervision of Instruction and School Management", (2016)
- Ward, A., "The learning Relationship: Learning and Development for Relationship-Based Practice", (2012)
- Solomon, Mkpuma, "Supervisory Skills Required of Principals in Order to Ensure Effective Management of Instruction in Abakaliki Education Zone of Ebonyi State", (2015)